

Analog FeedForward Equalizer Optimization in the Context of 50G-PON

DYLAN CHEVALIER^{1,2,*}, PASCAL SCALART³, GAËL SIMON¹, JÉRÉMY POTET¹, LAURENT BRAMERIE², MICHEL JOINDOT², MATHILDE GAY², PHILIPPE CHANCLOU¹, AND MONIQUE THUAL²

¹Orange, 2 avenue Pierre Marzin, 22307 Lannion Cédex, France

²Univ Rennes, CNRS, Institut FOTON - UMR 6082, F-22300 Lannion, France

³Univ Rennes, IRISA - UMR 6074, F-22305 Lannion, France

* dylan.chevalier@orange.com

Compiled March 18, 2025

We address one of the challenges of 50 Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) implementation induced by the limited bandwidth of low-cost components and signal distortions of fiber transmission and photonic devices. In the context of the broadband access network, and more specifically 50G-PON, the simplest and cheapest solution is usually the best. Implementing Analog FeedForward Equalizer (AFFE) is not as simple as using Digital FeedForward Equalizer (DFFE) techniques but is relevant from a cost and energy consumption point of view. AFFE has a number of advantages, such as a lower power consumption and a lower latency, thanks to the fact that it avoids using an Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC). In this work, we focus on AFFE optimization techniques to mitigate InterSymbol Interference (ISI) and Chromatic Dispersion (CD), and therefore improve signal quality. We model an AFFE in order to reduce a complex problem (because of AFFE's inter-cells non-uniformity and intra-cells non-linearity for example) into a simpler formulation that can be solved according to a Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) approach. This approach is possible when the transmission channel does not fluctuate. Experimental validation through electrical and optical setups demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed optimization, achieving significant reduction in Bit Error Rate (BER) and opening eye diagrams for better signal clarity, thereby offering a viable solution for future optical networks.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/ao.XX.XXXXXX>

1. INTRODUCTION

The 50 Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) is the latest specification finalized by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) [1], offering a Downstream (DS) bitrate of 50 Gbit/s using Non-Return-to-Zero On-Off-Keying (NRZ-OOK) with a wavelength centered at 1342 ± 2 nm, and several options of Upstream (US) bitrates working at 12.5, 25, and 50 Gbit/s at 1286 ± 2 nm in case of a triple coexistence of Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (G-PON) [2], 10 Gigabit Symmetric capable Passive Optical Network (XGS-PON) [3], and 50G-PON [4]. The Passive Optical Network (PON) architecture involves an Optical Line Termination (OLT) located at a Central Office (CO) connected to multiple Optical Network Units (ONUs) in a point-to-multipoint topology, supporting up to 128 terminations over a typical distance of 20 km maximum. Inherited from previous PON generations, the DS signal is continuously transmitted in Time Division Multiplexing (TDM), while the US operates in Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) with Burst Mode (BM) operation, where each ONU transmits in

allocated time windows.

Legacy PONs depends largely on the pre-existence of mature high-volume, low-cost optical and electronic components. In 2020, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) standardized the 25 Gigabit capable Ethernet Passive Optical Network (25G-EPON)[5]. The 25G-EPON was the inaugural TDM-PON using datacenter technologies. Today cost-effective 25G components are abundant, including Electro Absorption Modulated Lasers (EMLs), Directly Modulated Lasers (DMLs), and Avalanche PhotoDiodes (APDs). Additionally, electrical components such as TransImpedance Amplifiers (TIAs) and Serializer/Deserializers (SER/DESS) technology can be repurposed from data center technologies [6].

The ITU-T 50G-PON faces significant constraints due to the limited bandwidth of cost-effective transmitters and receivers (i.e., 25G class receivers used for 50 Gbit/s signal) [7], as well as the challenges of noise and Chromatic Dispersion (CD), which lead to signal distortions and InterSymbol Interference (ISI). To address these issues, channel equalization techniques have been integrated into PON specifications for the first time. Digital Sig-

nal Processing (DSP) has been the community's main concern since the 50G-PON introduction. One of the most commonly used architectures is the Digital FeedForward Equalizer (DFFE). It is designed to mitigate ISI by pre-emphasizing received signals based on past transmitted symbols, thus enhancing signal integrity and overall data transmission performance [8]. The first prototype of real-time symmetrical 50G-PON [9] was based on a DSP architecture. It requires an Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) and an equalizer before the transmission (7 taps for OLT, 15 taps for ONU). At the receiver side, a Clock Data Recovery (CDR) was required and equalization was done by combining DFFE and Maximum Likelihood Sequence Estimation (MLSE) approaches. The ITU-T introduced Transmitter and Dispersion Eye Closure (TDEC) to qualify transmitter penalties by emulating a limited optical receiver with an 18.75 GHz 4th-order Bessel-Thompson low-pass filter, as recommended in [1]. It assumes the use of a DFFE with 13 taps for DS and 7 taps for US [10, 11]. Despite the high performance of DSP-based DFFE solutions, their energy requirements are significant compared with Analog Signal Processing (ASP) alternatives.

In the early days of XGS-PON, research was carried out adding an Analog FeedForward Equalizer (AFFE) to limit the CD and help the TIA [12] which were the first two limiting factors at the time. Recent research focused on AFFE to provide a low-cost, energy-efficient solution [13]. While there are numerous articles in the literature on the architecture of AFFEs [14–17], very few of them focus on optimizing the parameter settings of these architectures due to the multitude of possible settings. Software solutions are generally supplied by manufacturers, enabling cell indexes to be optimized from the S_{21} measurements of the transmission channel, thus corresponding to a Zero Forcing (ZF) approach. In practice, this solution corresponds to a sub-optimal approach as it aims to set the ISI to zero in a noise free case without taking into account the presence of noise into the received signal. In [18], another approach is presented in which the indexes of each cell are varied from -120 to +120 in steps of 40, except for cell 2, which remains at +120. Bit Error Rate (BER) is measured at each change. The major drawback of this method is that it relies on statistical measurements of the BER for each range, which requires numerous time-consuming calculations and thus leads to a lack of precision in the setting of the coefficients. In [15], a "brute force" solution is presented, where the proposed algorithm tests all solutions, keeping the middle cell with the highest value. The problem with this solution is that it is computationally expensive and not robust to noise.

Recently, there has been a real growing interest in ASP in PON with the first analog 50G-PON prototype being proposed [19]. The advantage of analog equalization is its very low power consumption (< 250 mW) for bitrates below 64 Gbit/s [20, 21]. It does not require an ADC, thereby reducing power consumption, particularly given that an ADC operating at this bitrate can consume between 600 and 2000 mW [22, 23]. This is why we oriented our choice to ASP with AFFE. However, equalization with an AFFE includes management of its "imperfections", which are not present with a DFFE as for example limited bandwidth of each cell, inter-cell non-uniformity and intra-cell non-linearity of the impulse responses and amplifiers leakage (detailed in Section 2). In the context of the PON, "history" showed that the simplest and cheapest solution is always the one adopted.

This article proposes a novel approach for optimizing the AFFE cell weights to compensate for transmission channel limitations. This proposed solution is possible when the transmis-

sion channel does not fluctuate, since adaptation is not done in real-time. Such approach is based on a mathematical modeling of the AFFE operation, as well as the introduction of specific simplifying assumptions that make the problem easier to solve with an Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE)-based approach and Least Mean Squares (LMS) algorithm. The LMS equalization approaches are known to provide a trade-off between channel-noise amplification and ISI mitigation, accounting for the unique characteristics of ASP components. Traditional optimization methods, such as the ZF approach, have shown limitations in achieving ideal parameter convergence in previous experiments [24]. Therefore, the proposed method provides a more effective solution for AFFE optimization, ensuring improved performance and energy efficiency in 50G-PON systems. This paper is an extension of our prior work [25].

In Section 2, we present the DFFE, followed by the AFFE. We then discuss the problems that come up when implementing it in an optical receiver. Section 3 is devoted to the mathematical modeling of the AFFE which account for the imperfections of its analog nature. In Section 4, several assumptions are made to make the equalizing problem easier to solve and a first solution (i.e. an algorithm) is proposed to take into account the imperfections of the AFFE cells. This algorithm's proof-of-concept is first validated with an electrical setup and then with an optical setup (see Section 5). Although this version of the algorithm performs well in minimizing ISI without considering the average power available at AFFE output. Section 6 presents an enhanced version to the proposed algorithm by introducing regularization constraints forcing the AFFE to maximize its output power. The main results and conclusion of this study are discussed in Section 7.

2. FEEDFORWARD EQUALIZER (FFE)

As mentioned in Section 1, ITU-T has introduced equalization into 50G-PON for the first time. The simplest solution in terms of cost and complexity is the Feed-Forward Equalizer (FFE). In this Section, we present the FFE in both the digital (DFFE) and analog (AFFE) domain.

A. Digital FeedForward Equalizer (DFFE)

Introduced in the 1960s, the Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter is a common type of digital filter architecture [26, 27]. The structure of an DFFE is a type of FIR filter mitigating ISI. The input signal $x[n]$ goes through a series of taps (delays) and is multiplied by a corresponding coefficient (weight) b_k for each delayed version of the signal. The output of the FIR is a linear combination of these delayed inputs, see Fig. 1. The output signal $y[n]$ is expressed in Eq. 1 as the sum of the b_k tap coefficients multiplied by the k -shifted input signal $x[n]$. N corresponds to the total number of delays/taps in the architecture and z^{-1} , the unit delay operator of the Z-transform. The response of the DFFE is a linear combination of the responses of each of its taps. This is only possible if the taps are linear. For example, if we consider that b_3 is equal to 50, doubling this value will result in b_3 at 100, which is not the case for the AFFE. By finding the optimal taps (b_0 to b_{N-1}), DFFE has a frequency response that will mitigate ISI caused by channel distortions.

$$y[n] = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} b_k \times x[n-k] \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. General N^{th} -order DFFE structure.

B. Analog FeedForward Equalizer (AFFE)

The purpose of this Section is to illustrate the specific features of an AFFE by comparing it to the DFFE. The AFFE offers a considerable advantage in terms of latency and energy efficiency, since the received signal is processed directly in the analog domain without the need for ADCs, making it interesting for high bitrates in PON. Unlike DFFE, which requires signal parallelization at a lower bitrate, the addition of ADCs and, therefore, increased power consumption due to analog/digital conversions, AFFE guarantees signal rate response and simplicity of hardware design. In the present work, we consider a specific AFFE, namely the C681B from SHF Communication Technologies AG. However, the proposed modeling methodology (in Section 3) as well as the proposed optimization algorithm (in Section 4) can be applied to any AFFE. To model the AFFE's operation, we consider the general architecture of the DFFE, however, it will be applied in the analog domain leading to an AFFE whose structure is shown in Fig. 2. The AFFE used in this work has 6 cells. The output signal $y(t)$ is the sum of the $k\tau$ -shifted (τ : delay) input signal $x(t)$ times gain coefficients G_k with $k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$ (Similar to $\{b_0, \dots, b_{N-1}\}$ for a DFFE). These gains are realized with built-in variable gain amplifiers. In the digital domain (DFFE), the term "tap" corresponds to a coefficient associated with a discrete delay (z^{-1}) defined by the sampling period. In the analog domain, the signal is processed in the continuous domain, without sampling or discrete delays. Delays are implemented using analog components (physical delays), which do not correspond to an index shift (DFFE) and therefore do not directly align with the concept of a "tap". Consequently, we will refer in this work to the term of "cells" to avoid any confusion. For each of the six cells, the value corresponding to the cell's amplitude will be referred to as an index that should be defined via a control software. For a given cell k ($k = 0, \dots, 5$), the corresponding index j_k takes values from -127 to +127, i.e., 255 indexes are possible.

Fig. 3 and Eq. 2 show the more general form of AFFE. The output signal $y(t)$ is equal to the sum of the impulse responses of each cell $h_k(t)$ convolved ($*$ in Eq. 2) with the input signal $x(t)$. An important point to emphasize is that the AFFE impulse response $h(t)$ obtained is not the sum of the impulse responses $h_k(t)$ of a shifted version of an elementary response (detailed further in this Section). In equalization, the optimal receiver in the MMSE sense involves a DFFE that realizes a weighted sum of delayed signals, and there is a reason: the equalizer works on the sampled signal.

Fig. 2. Structure of the AFFE used for this study.

Fig. 3. General N^{th} -order AFFE structure. In our study, $N = 6$.

$$y(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x(t) * h_k(t) \quad (2)$$

As mentioned in Section 1, four imperfections of the AFFE listed below are considered in this work.

- Limited bandwidth** of each cell, see Fig. 4. Regarding DFFE, the bandwidth of each tap is considered infinite. AFFE, on the other hand, is made up of amplifiers which, by definition, have a finite bandwidth. In Fig. 4, we plot the module of the frequency response of the cell $k = 0$ and index $j_0 = 10$ (blue curve). We can see that cells have a finite bandwidth, i.e. they can be considered as a low-pass filter.
- Inter-cell non-uniformity** of the impulse responses. Fig. 5a shows the impulse response of each cell (SHF C681B) for the same index ($j_k = 100$). In this example, each impulse response is normalized by its Euclidean norm so that the resulting mean power of each impulse response is equal to one. The same behavior is observed in Fig. 5b with another AFFE (Analog Devices HMC6545) for an index $j_k = 50$. For a given index, the greater the cell (cell 0 to cell 6), the greater the attenuation of the impulse response, i.e. the gain is not constant.
- Intra-cell non-linearity** of the impulse responses. As shown in Fig. 6, the peak amplitudes of the impulse responses of the indexes ($h_{0,j_0}(t)$ in Fig. 6) for a single cell, exhibit a linear zone (from -65 to +65) and two non-linear zones at extreme

indexes (inferior to -65 and superior to +65). For example, in Fig. 6, at index +50, we have an amplitude of 0.15 and at index +100, we expect an amplitude of 0.3, but we obtain an amplitude of 0.35.

4. Leakage. In a DFFE, the global impulse response is the sum of the impulse responses of the taps, and therefore, when all taps are set to zero, the output is null. For the AFFE under study, leakage is observed when all amplifiers are set to zero. There is an isolation problem, i.e., when the gain is set to zero, it does not correspond to an infinite attenuation. Because of this, a simple sum is not allowed. In Fig. 4, we can observe that the module of the frequency response when all cells are set to zero (yellow curve) has a non-negligible amplitude over the whole band. If we subtract the leakage, we see a clear difference between the module of the frequency response with (blue curve) and without the leakage (orange curve). Leak management is discussed in detail in Section 3.

Fig. 4. Module of frequency responses ($|H(f)|$) in dB of cell $k = 0$ index $j_0 = 10$ with (blue curve) and without (orange curve) leakage and when all cells have an index $j_k = 0$ (yellow curve) (Imperfections 1 and 4).

3. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE ANALOG FEED-FORWARD EQUALIZER

In our study, the AFFE output is expressed by Eq. 3. The output $y(t)$ is the sum of the input signal $x(t)$ convolved with the impulse responses, $h_{k,j_k}(t)$, of cell k at index j_k (values between -127 and +127). Compared to Eq. 2, we consider the j_k index inside the impulse response $h_{k,j_k}(t)$ because j_k is relative to the cell k . As we saw on Fig 5, for the same index from one cell to another, the maximum of the impulse response is different (imperfection 2 and 3: inter-cell non-uniformity and intra-cell non-linearity).

$$y(t) = \sum_{k=0}^5 x(t) * h_{k,j_k}(t) \quad (3)$$

The impulse response for a given cell k at a given index j_k is measured using a Vectorial Networks Analyzer (VNA) by setting all indexes of the 5 remaining cells (i.e. others than k) to zero. Once the S-parameters are available, the S_{21} frequency

Fig. 5. Energy-normalized impulse response of each individual cell for a) SHF C681BB AFFE with an index set to 100 b) Analog Devices HMC6545 AFFE with an index at 50. Both Figures show "imperfection 2".

Fig. 6. Peak amplitude of cell 0 impulse responses h_{0,j_0} as function of index j_0 (Imperfection 3).

response provides the impulse response $h_{k,j_k}^{meas}(t)$. Such analysis is conducted for each cell k ($k = 0, \dots, 5$) and for each index setting ($j_k = -127, \dots, +127$). The first step is to be able to reconstruct the global impulse response for a set of cells' indexes by summing the various Transfer Functions (TFs) of each cell.

A. Leakage management

The leakage management, imperfection 4, presented in Section 2, is detailed in this Section. Let us consider a given set of cells' indexes j_k within the interval $[-127, +127]$. We seek to reconstruct the global TF of the AFFE by summing the different TFs of cells to match to the global TF measured with a VNA. In first time, we obtained the global AFFE TF through S_{21} VNA measurements. Such TF is represented in Fig 7 (blue curve). In second time, the global TF obtained by summing offline each individual cell frequency response (i.e. the Fourier Transform of the sum of impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{meas}(t)$) is represented in Fig. 7 (yellow curve). The differences that can be observed between these two TFs (blue versus yellow) are due to the leakage phenomenon. This behavior is similar to a switch that would not produce a null signal at its output when open, see Fig. 4. For each S-parameter measure of the cells' indexes, the leakage $\zeta(t)$ is present. To remove it, we simply need to subtract from all cells TFs the value $\zeta(t)$ which corresponds to the impulse response when all cells are set to zero, i.e., $\zeta(t) = \sum_{k=0}^5 h_{k,0}^{meas}(t)$. Thus, Fig. 7 shows that the sum of the individual TF minus the leak (purple) matches very well with the global TF without leak (orange). To simplify the equations, we assume that leakage is removed from the impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{meas}(t)$, i.e. $h_{k,j_k}(t) = h_{k,j_k}^{meas}(t) - \zeta(t)$.

Fig. 7. Module of the Transfer Function (TF) ($|H(f)|$) in dB of a given set of cell indexes with and without taking into account the leak (Imperfection 4).

B. Analog FeedForward Equalizer linearization

The next step is to make the AFFE linear as it would be with a DFFE, taking into account the inter/intra-cell non-linearities (imperfections 2 and 3, presented in Section 2). To do so, we propose for each cell k and j_k index impulse response to calculate the Euclidean norm ($\|\cdot\|$), or in other words, the square root of the impulse response ($h_{k,j_k}(t)$) energy, in order to normalize the impulse responses, see Eq. 4.

$$h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t) = \frac{h_{k,j_k}(t)}{c_{k,j_k}} \quad \text{with} \quad c_{k,j_k} = \|h_{k,j_k}(t)\| \quad (4)$$

By retracing Fig. 5, but this time with normalized impulse responses, we obtain Fig. 8. We can see that for the same index, the impulse responses are well normalized, and that there is no

longer a significant gap between cell 0 and cell 5 as we observe on Fig. 5.

Fig. 8. Impulse response of each individual cell for a given index after normalization.

Since this model makes the AFFE linear, we now want to determine the j_k indexes that will affect $h_{k,j_k}(t)$ and c_{k,j_k} . The hypothesis of local invariant impulse responses regarding the index j_k allows us to reduce the problem and deal only with the coefficients c_{k,j_k} . To demonstrate that the normalized impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)$ are indeed invariant relatively to index j_k , we calculate the Relative Modeling Error (RME) expressed in Eq. 5:

$$RME(j_k, m) = \frac{\|h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t) - h_{k,j_k-m}^{(n)}(t)\|^2}{\|h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)\|^2} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

RME is the ratio of the difference between the normalized impulse response of index j_k and the normalized impulse response of index $j_k - m$ ($m \in [-20, +20]$ in Fig. 9) divided by the squared norm of the normalized impulse response. For example, when $k = 0$, $j_0 = 100$ and $m = 0$, we compute the RME of the normalized impulse response of cell 0 and index 100 to itself, and when $k = 0$, $j_0 = 100$ and $m = -5$, we calculate the RME of the normalized impulse response of cell 0 and index +100 to the normalized impulse response of cell 0 and index +95. Examples of RMEs are shown in Fig. 9. It can be seen that locally around the index j_k (± 20), the RME is 0.02%. We can therefore deduce that normalized impulse responses are invariant relative to index j_k . Normalized impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}$ no longer vary, only coefficients c_{k,j_k} vary according to j_k . In other words, $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}$ is equal to $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}$ locally around j_k (e.g. $h_{0,100}^{(n)}(t) \approx h_{0,105}^{(n)}(t)$). The problem becomes linear through the use of c_{k,j_k} coefficients, enabling the application of an MMSE equalizer.

Fig. 10 shows c_{k,j_k} coefficients as a function of cells' indexes j_k for each cell k . This also shows the inter-cell non-uniformity and intra-cell non-linearity (imperfection 2 and 3, see Fig. 5 and 6), i.e. the energy between different cells for the same index. $c_{j,k} \in \mathcal{U}$ with $\text{card}(\mathcal{U}) = 255$ corresponding to the number of cells' indexes available.

Later, for optimization, when the index j_k is smaller than or equal to 0, we invert the sign of $c_{j,k}$ and $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)$. This step is

Fig. 9. Example of RME study as function of different cells k and indexes j_k .

important as it will enable us to distinguish between a positive and a negative index. This is only possible if the TFs are similar, as we demonstrate with the invariance of normalized impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)$. In the following, for the adaptation algorithm (see Section 4), we need a decision circuit to make a decision on the received bit. An Automatic Gain Control (AGC) is added to normalize the received signal and enable a correct decision to be made.

Fig. 10. c_{k,j_k} coefficients computed with impulse responses (plain curves) and modified for the optimization (dashed curves).

The mathematical AFFE modeling can be expressed by Eq. 6 (see Fig. 11). The impulse response of the AFFE is therefore a linear combination of six normalized impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)$ with coefficients c_{k,j_k} (with $c_{k,j_k} = \|h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)\|$) and the leakage (ξ). In the following work, we focus on the search for optimal coefficients c_{k,j_k} based on the principle of the descent gradient algorithm [8] to improve signal quality.

$$h_{\text{AFFE}}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} c_{k,j_k} \times h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t) + \xi(t) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 11. Proposed model for the AFFE.

4. ADAPTATION ALGORITHM

The adaptation process shown consists of two steps: 1. Offline indexes optimization (Fig. 12) and 2. Experimental incorporation of indexes in the AFFE. The algorithm proposed to optimize AFFE is not able to follow the fluctuations of a transmission channel in real time, it can only be tuned to be optimal for an unknown, but stable, channel. For this first step, we sample the input signal at a period T_s . The samples are fed into the AFFE numerical model, which reproduces the model shown in Eq. 6 and Fig. 11. It is important to note that the normalized impulse responses $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}(t)$ presented in Section 3 are sampled at a period T_s . In Fig. 12, the output signal of the AFFE numerical model is then decimated by a factor Q ($Q = 2$ in our experiments) to provide an output signal that is sampled at the symbol rate (i.e., T-spaced) before being adjusted in mean power using an AGC. The AGC is used to adapt the amplitude at the output of the AFFE so that a decision can then be made around the decision threshold. A decision is then taken at the decision circuit, where the error is calculated and used by the LMS algorithm. For reasons of simplicity and low computational requirements, we chose the LMS algorithm, which we modify in order to find the optimal c_{k,j_k} coefficients. Indeed, the LMS algorithm is designed to approximate a solution that is optimized according to the Mean Squared Error (MSE), see Eq. 7 where $e[i]$ is the error calculated at the border of the decision circuit, \underline{c} a vector with associated values for each cell ($c_{0,j_0}, \dots, c_{5,j_5}$) and G the AGC, within an adaptive filtering framework. This approach is robust when there is noise, which is the case when reaching low sensitivities in the PON. At each iteration, the LMS algorithm will update the c_{k,j_k} coefficients, see Eq. 8 as well as G , see Eq. 9. $\underline{z}[n]$ is a vector with associated values for each cell ($z_0[n], \dots, z_5[n]$), see Fig. 12. Once the algorithm has converged to the indexes, we move on to the second stage, which consists of experimentally incorporating the indexes j_k into the AFFE.

$$\mathcal{J}(\underline{c}, G) = \mathbb{E} \left(e^2[i] \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{c}[i+1] &= \underline{c}[i] - \mu_{\text{AFFE}} \times \nabla_{\underline{c}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{c}, G) \\ \text{with } \nabla_{\underline{c}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{c}, G) &= -2 \times \mathbb{E}(e[i] \underline{z}[i]) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 12. Indexes optimization processing.

$$G[i+1] = G[i] - \mu_G \times \nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G) \quad (9)$$

with $\nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G) = -2 \times \mathbb{E}(e[i]y[i])$

A pseudo-code version of the algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1. First, we define the step for the adaptation of the c_{k,j_k} coefficients, $\mu_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}$ and the AGC adaptation (G), μ_G . The step must be relatively small in order to always remain in the local area where normalized impulse responses are invariant. In our experimental setup, we chose $\mu_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}$ equal to 4×10^{-5} . The six c_{k,j_k} coefficients are initialized randomly ($c_{k,j_k} \in \mathcal{U}$) in $\underline{\mathbf{c}}$. The sampled signal $x[n]$ is convolved (*) with the normalized impulse responses of each cell $h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}[n]$ (see Line 5). All outputs $z_k[n]$ ($k = 0, \dots, 5$), are integrated into a single vector \mathbf{z} (see Line 6). The AFFE output $y[n]$ is equal to the dot product of vectors $\mathbf{z}[n]$ and $\underline{\mathbf{c}}[i]$ (see Line 9). The AFFE output is then decimated by the oversampling factor Q (see Line 7) and multiplied by a gain factor G (see Line 10). To optimize the cell's indexes, the error $e[i]$ at the decision circuit is computed. It is defined as the difference between the estimated symbol at receiver $\hat{a}[i]$ and the output $u[i]$ of the AGC (see Line 12). Then, using stochastic approximation (see Line 13) of the MSE cost function in Eq. 8 and Eq. 9, the AGC coefficient $G[i]$ (see Line 18) and the cells' coefficients vector $\underline{\mathbf{c}}[i]$ (see Line 14), i.e. the vector $(c_{0,j_0}[i], \dots, c_{5,j_5}[i])$, are updated at each iteration using a first-order gradient algorithm (see Line 14 and Line 18). Since the obtained update of $c_k[i+1]$ is a real number, we estimate its nearest neighbor belonging to the discrete alphabet \mathcal{U} (see Line 15) with $\text{card}(\mathcal{U}) = 255$. As a result, the final value of the coefficient $c_k[i+1]$ in Line 16 corresponds to a discrete variable and no longer to a continuous variable (a quantization error is therefore added in Eq. 10 and Line 15).

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket, j_k^* = \underset{j_k \in \llbracket -127, +127 \rrbracket}{\text{argmin}} \|c_k[i+1] - c_{k,j_k}\|^2 \quad (10)$$

5. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

In this Section, we validate our algorithm in a experimental setup. Our adaptation algorithm was first validated with an electrical setup, then with an optical setup.

Algorithm 1. AFFE optimization

```

1: Input:  $x, \mu_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}, \mu_G$ 
2: Variables:  $L \leftarrow$  size of the frame,  $N \leftarrow 6$ 
3: Initialize the AFFE:  $\underline{\mathbf{c}} \in \mathcal{U}^6, G \in \mathbb{R}, Q \in \mathbb{N}$ 
4: while  $n \leq L$  do
5:    $z_k[n] \leftarrow h_{k,j_k}^{(n)}[n] * x[n], \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$ 
6:    $\mathbf{z}[n] \leftarrow (z_0[n], \dots, z_5[n])$ 
7:    $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \text{decimate}(\mathbf{y}, Q)$  ▷ Decimation
8:    $\mathbf{z} \leftarrow \text{decimate}(\mathbf{z}, Q)$ 
9:    $\mathbf{y}[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{z}^T[i] \times \underline{\mathbf{c}}[i]$  ▷ Output of the AFFE
10:   $u[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{y}[i] \times G[i]$ 
11:   $\hat{a}[i] \leftarrow \text{decision}(u[i])$  ▷ Decision
12:   $e[i] \leftarrow \hat{a}[i] - u[i]$  ▷ Error
13:   $\nabla_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G) \leftarrow -2e[i] \times \mathbf{z}[i]$ 
14:   $\underline{\mathbf{c}}[i+1] \leftarrow \underline{\mathbf{c}}[i] - \mu_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}} \times \nabla_{\underline{\mathbf{c}}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G)$ 
15:   $j_k^* = \text{argmin} \|c_k[i+1] - c_{k,j_k}\|^2, \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$ 
16:   $c_k[i+1] \leftarrow c_{k,j_k^*}, \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$ 
17:   $\nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G) \leftarrow -2e[i] \times \mathbf{y}[i]$ 
18:   $G[i+1] \leftarrow G[i] - \mu_G \times \nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\underline{\mathbf{c}}, G)$ 

```

A. Electrical Validation

A.1. Experimental setup

The electrical experimental setup is presented in Fig. 13. An electrical real-time Non-Return-to-Zero (NRZ) signal is generated with a Pulse Pattern Generator (PPG) with a bitrate of 50 Gbit/s. To emulate the low-pass filtering effect of the low-cost components within the transmitting chain, a Bessel filter with a cutoff frequency of 13 GHz is inserted between Transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx). At the Rx side, equalization is performed using AFFE. The search for the AFFE optimal cells is carried out by first capturing the received signal with a Real-Time Oscilloscope (RTO) at a sampling rate of 100 GSa/s and a bandwidth of 33 GHz, and then searching for the optimal AFFE cells' indexes using the offline algorithm presented in Section 4. BER is measured with an Error Detector (ED) and eye diagrams with a Digital Communication Analyzer (DCA).

A.2. Results

Eye diagrams before and after the AFFE are represented respectively in Fig. 14.a and 14.b. When a 50 Gbit/s signal goes through the 13 GHz filter, we can see the effect of ISI (Fig. 14.a). Before equalization, we obtain a BER at 2.5×10^{-6} . After equalization, the ISI is reduced, the eye is opened and finally, *error free* (BER $< 10^{-9}$) is obtained (considered for a BER below 10^{-9}). It is important to emphasize that the target BER in PON is 10^{-2} . This limit corresponds to the 50G-PON standard Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) Forward Error Correction (FEC) threshold.

B. Optical Validation

B.1. Experimental setup

The experimental setup used for the optical part is shown in Fig. 13 with the addition of part b). The same electrical signal presented above is generated, then a 23 dB gain electrical amplifier with a 3 dB bandwidth of 55 GHz is used to drive the EML. The emitter chipset is composed of a Distributed FeedBack laser (DFB), integrated with an Electro-Absorption Modulator (EAM) and a Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA) cascaded [28]. The output signal has an Extinction Ratio (ER) of 7.12 dB and a wavelength of 1341 nm (worst dispersion range is 77.1 ps/nm in Standard Single Mode Fiber (SSMF) defined in [1]). A 12 dBm

Fig. 13. Experimental setup to validate in a) the electrical field, then in the optical field by adding b).

Fig. 14. Eye diagrams obtained before and after AFFE in electrical a,b) and optical c,d,e,f).

optical power signal is sent into 0 or 10 km of SSMF. A Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) is added before a coupler to control the Received Optical Power (ROP) ("PWM" in Fig. 13) at the photodiode input. For reasons of photodiode availability, the Optical-Electrical (OE) conversion is performed with a 40 GHz bandwidth Positive Intrinsic Negative (PIN) photodiode. To emulate the low-pass filtering effect of the low-cost components within the transmitting chain, a Bessel filter with a cutoff frequency of 13 GHz is kept. In the 50G-PON ITU-T context, the use of class 25G APD with about an 18 GHz bandwidth is preferred [1].

B.2. Results

Fig. 14c and 14e show the eye diagrams at the AFFE input in Back-to-Back (BtB) and 10 km of fiber respectively. We can see that the signal suffers from the ISIs (mainly due to the 13 GHz filter) as expected. A BER of 10^{-4} was observed in BtB and 10^{-3} for 10 km of fiber at the AFFE input. The time evolution of the MSE is represented in Fig. 16a where each point is obtained averaging in each frame of 64 consecutive samples the squared error measured (see Eq. 7) at the decision circuit. We can see that the steady-state behavior of the MSE is around -10 dB. Once the algorithm has converged to an optimal solution, the cell indexes are retrieved and set into the AFFE. When this procedure is

carried out in BtB and for 10 km of fiber, we can see in Fig. 14d and 14f that horizontal and vertical openings of the eye diagrams are wider and larger enabling the receiver to better select optimal decision threshold and sampling time at the decision circuit. After equalization, we obtain a BER of 7×10^{-9} and 2×10^{-6} in BtB and for 10 km of fiber respectively. This confirms that the algorithm managed to optimize the AFFE indexes in order to improve the transmitted signal's quality.

In Fig. 16b, the time evolution of the six indexes of the AFFE is represented. We can see that the initial time convergence of the coefficients is relatively fast since the optimization algorithm requires no more than 1 μ s (\approx 75000 iterations) to converge towards the optimal indexes solution. Compared with the 50G-PON standard [1], the adaptation is not fast enough, since the preamble length is a maximum of 611 ns. This adaptation time depends on two factors: the adaptation step μ_c/μ_G and initialization. We can hope to reduce this convergence time by increasing the adaptation step and making a special study of indexes initialization. From 500 ns, the variance of the estimated indexes is relatively low indicating that a stable local minimum has been found by the LMS algorithm.

Fig. 16c shows the module of the channel frequency response without the AFFE (blue), with the AFFE (orange) and the AFFE frequency response (yellow) in dB obtained after index opti-

mization for 0 km of optical fiber. We can first observe that the channel bandwidth is improved (a -3 dB cutoff frequency of 12 GHz before and 33 GHz after equalization). Secondly, the AFFE global frequency response provides gain in the frequencies of interest. Fig. 15 shows BER curves, measured with the ED, in BtB (blue curves) and with 10 km (orange curves) of SSMF as a function of the ROP before (dotted curves) and after (solid line curves) AFFE optimization. First, the impact of adding optical fiber can be seen in the 1.2 dB loss in sensitivity (BER at 10^{-2}). By adding the AFFE, we run the algorithm for each ROP to find the optimal indexes, incorporate them into the AFFE and measure the BER. We can see that the addition of AFFE improves BER at every ROP, especially when it is very low, i.e. with a lower Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). At a BER of 10^{-2} , the AFFE improves sensitivity by 1.2 dB in BtB and with 10 km of optical fiber.

Fig. 15. BER as a function of the ROP in dBm for 0 and 10 km of optical fiber with and without AFFE.

AFFE optimization works very well. However, when there are 10 km of optical fiber, an amplitude loss can be observed compared to BtB (see Fig. 14d) for the same received optical power, see Fig. 14c and 14e. The spectral density of the signal has been improved, but the AFFE output amplitude has decreased. In other words, the eye diagram after equalization is better than before equalization, but compared with the BtB, the amplitude is lower. In the context of 50G-PON, ONUs are located up to 20 km far from the OLT, resulting in signals with a lower SNR. The AFFE output power must therefore be maximized to be above the sensitivity of the ED. This is the subject of Section 6.

6. POWER CONSTRAINT LEAST MEAN SQUARE (LMS) ALGORITHM

To maximize the AFFE output power, we need to force the algorithm to use higher $c_{k,jk}$ coefficients, i.e. cells's indexes with higher energy (see Fig. 10). In the model proposed by Eq. 6, when the AGC (gain G) is high, it means that the signal before the AGC is low (the indexes of cells with low energy) and conversely, when the AGC is low, it means that the signal before the AGC is high (the indexes of cells with more energy). The interesting case for maximizing AFFE output amplitude is the second, i.e. when the cells have high indexes. To do this, we

modify the cost function in Eq. 7 by adding the expected value of G squared, see Eq. 11:

$$\mathcal{J}_{const.}(\mathbf{c}, G) = \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G) + \lambda \times \mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G) \quad (11)$$

With $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G) = \mathbb{E}(e^2[i])$ (see Eq. 7), $\mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G) = \mathbb{E}(G^2[i])$ and λ , a pondering factor. λ allows $\nabla_G \mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$ to be brought up to the same level as $\nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G)$. A compromise has to be found for λ , a λ that is too weak will not allow the constraint on the AGC to be taken into account, and a λ too high will not allow the decision error to be taken into account.

When G is high, $\mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$ will increase the cost function, and when it is low, $\mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$ tends to decrease. To minimize $\mathcal{J}_{const.}(\mathbf{c}, G)$, the algorithm has to do a trade-off between $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G)$ and $\mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$, i.e. it will look for a solution that leads to a low value of $\mathcal{J}_{const.}(\mathbf{c}, G)$ but for a low value of $\mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$. Since $G[i]$ can be expressed as the ratio of $y[i]$ (before the AGC) to $u[i]$ (after the AGC), see Fig. 12, it is sufficient to calculate $\nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$, see Eq. 12. This new version is shown on Algorithm 2. The difference between Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 is located in line 13, where $\nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G)$ is incorporated.

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}_G(\mathbf{c}, G) = -2 \times \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{u^2[i]}{y^3[i]} \times \mathbf{z}[i] \right) \quad (12)$$

By running Algorithm 1 several times for the electrical validation with a different adaptation step ($\mu_{\mathbf{c}}$), AGC and indexes for each cell at initialization, we find ourselves in the case shown in Fig. 17a. We can see that the eye diagram has been improved, however, there is less power at the output of the AFFE. By adding the constraint with Algorithm 2, see Fig. 17b, we can see that there is more power at the output of the AFFE. The loss of power that Algorithm 1 leads to results in a reduction in BER with a measured 8.9×10^{-7} compared with *error free* with Algorithm 2. This result shows that this new version of the algorithm works well.

Algorithm 2. Power constraint AFFE optimization

- 1: **Input:** $x, \mu_{\mathbf{c}}, \mu_G$
- 2: **Variables:** $L \leftarrow \text{size of the frame}, N \leftarrow 6$
- 3: **Initialize the AFFE:** $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{U}^6, G \in \mathbb{R}, Q \in \mathbb{N}, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$
- 4: **while** $n \leq L$ **do**
- 5: $z_k[n] \leftarrow h_{k,jk}^{(n)}[n] * x[n], \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$
- 6: $\mathbf{z}[n] \leftarrow (z_0[n], \dots, z_5[n])$
- 7: $y \leftarrow \text{decimate}(y, Q)$ ▷ Decimation
- 8: $\mathbf{z} \leftarrow \text{decimate}(\mathbf{z}, Q)$
- 9: $y[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{z}^T[i] \times \mathbf{c}[i]$ ▷ Output of the AFFE
- 10: $u[i] \leftarrow y[i] \times G[i]$
- 11: $\hat{a}[i] \leftarrow \text{decision}(u[i])$ ▷ Decision
- 12: $e[i] \leftarrow \hat{a}[i] - u[i]$ ▷ Error
- 13: $\nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}_{const.}(\mathbf{c}, G) \leftarrow -2e[i] \times \mathbf{z}[i] - 2\lambda \times u[i]^2 / y[i]^3 \times \mathbf{z}[i]$
- 14: $\mathbf{c}[i+1] \leftarrow \mathbf{c}[i] - \mu_{\mathbf{c}} \times \nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \mathcal{J}_{const.}(\mathbf{c}, G)$
- 15: $\hat{j}_k^* = \text{argmin} \|c_k[i+1] - c_{k,jk}\|^2, \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$
- 16: $c_k[i+1] \leftarrow c_{k,\hat{j}_k^*}, \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$
- 17: $\nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G) \leftarrow -2e[i] \times y[i]$
- 18: $G[i+1] \leftarrow G[i] - \mu_G \times \nabla_G \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{c}, G)$

7. CONCLUSION

In this study, we presented an innovative approach to optimizing AFFE for 50G-PON using a MMSE method. We addressed critical challenges posed by the limited bandwidth and signal

Fig. 16. Temporal evolution of a) the MSE and b) Cells' indexes and c) Module of the frequency responses ($|H(f)|$) in dB of the channel without the AFFE (blue), with the AFFE (orange) and of the AFFE (yellow).

Fig. 17. Eye diagrams with obtained from a) Algorithm 1 with no power constraint and b) Algorithm 2 with power constraint.

distortions inherent in cost-effective optical network components. By focusing on the analog domain, we aimed to offer a low-cost, energy-efficient alternative to DSP techniques, which consume more energy.

The proposed method leverages the characteristics of ASP components to balance noise amplification and ISI reduction effectively compared to a ZF approach. We demonstrated the feasibility of our approach through a series of experimental validations, both in electrical and optical domains. The results confirmed significant improvements in signal integrity, evidenced by the reduction in BER and the opening of eye diagrams, which indicate clearer signal transmission.

One of the notable achievements of this work is the successful implementation of AFFE optimization in a 50G-PON setup. This advancement is particularly relevant given the increasing demand for higher data rates and more efficient network architectures. The experimental setup, which included a 50 Gbit/s signal passing through a low-pass filter and subsequent equalization, highlighted the practical benefits of the proposed approach. The optimized AFFE cells' indexes resulted in *error free* transmission, meeting the stringent BER requirements of optical networks.

In conclusion, this work offers a promising direction for future enhancements in PON technology. By optimizing AFFEs, we can achieve performance and energy efficiency, addressing

the growing needs of high-speed optical communication systems. This work lays the groundwork for further exploration into advanced analog equalization techniques. Although this study focuses on the specific characteristics of PON, the presented results can be used for optimizing ASP in other network segments like the Point-to-Point (PtP) in the optical access network where the use of digital FFE or even AFFE is envisaged [29] and where the channel does not change.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was carried out as part of the Lab'Optic joint activities. The authors would also like to thank Sumitomo for the loan of the EML/SOA chipset.

FUNDING INFORMATION:

OCTAPUS HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 project (number: 101070009).

REFERENCES

1. "G.9804.3 : 50-gigabit-capable passive optical networks (50G-PON): Physical media dependent (PMD) layer specification," .
2. "G.984.2 : Gigabit-capable passive optical networks (G-PON): Physical media dependent (PMD) layer specification," .
3. "G.9807.1 : 10-gigabit-capable symmetric passive optical network (XGS-PON)," .
4. F. Saliou, G. Simon, S. Le Huerou, G. Vu-Brugier, I. Cano, D. Nettet, Z. Hong, R. Rosales, M. Bideau, J. Potet, G. Gaillard, D. Chevalier, J. Zandueta, G. Talli, and P. Chanclou, "Two approaches for triple coexistence of G-PON, XGS-PON, and 50G-PON systems with extended reach and a class-D ODN," pp. C97–C105. Conference Name: Journal of Optical Communications and Networking.
5. 802.3ca 2020, "IEEE standard for ethernet amendment 9: Physical layer specifications and management parameters for 25 Gb/s and 50 Gb/s passive optical networks," Conference Name: IEEE Std 802.3ca-2020 (Amendment to IEEE Std 802.3-2018 as amended by IEEE 802.3cb-2018, IEEE 802.3bt-2018, IEEE 802.3cd-2018, IEEE 802.3cn-2019, IEEE 802.3cg-2019, IEEE 802.3cq-2020, IEEE 802.3cm-2020, and IEEE 802.3ch-2020).
6. V. Houtsma and D. van Veen, "Higher-speed PONs based on data center technology and optics [invited]," pp. A98–A104. Conference Name: Journal of Optical Communications and Networking.
7. P. Torres-Ferrera, V. Ferrero, M. Valvo, and R. Gaudino, "Impact of the overall electrical filter shaping in next-generation 25 and 50 Gb/s PONs," pp. 493–505.

8. B. Widrow, "Adaptive filters," in *Aspects of Network and System Theory*, pp. 563–586, r.e. kalman and n. DeClariss, eds., holt, rinehart and winston ed.
9. J. Li, N. Wang, J. Zhu, N. Zhang, L. Hu, M. Yu, H. Yuan, and B. Li, "First real-time symmetric 50G TDM-PON prototype with high bandwidth and low latency," in *2023 Opto-Electronics and Communications Conference (OECC)*, pp. 1–4. ISSN: 2166-8892.
10. M. Casasco, G. Caruso, I. N. Cano, D. Nasset, M. Valvo, V. Ferrero, and R. Gaudino, "TDEC metric in 50G-PON: analytical and experimental investigation on several implementation aspects," pp. 480–487. Conference Name: Journal of Optical Communications and Networking.
11. G. Caruso, I. N. Cano, G. Talli, D. Nasset, and R. Gaudino, "Study of TDEC for 50G-PON upstream at 50 Gb/s in negative dispersion regime using 25G-class transceivers," in *2023 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, pp. 1–3.
12. D. Torrientes, P. Chanclou, F. Laurent, S. Tsyier, Y. Chang, B. Charbonnier, and C. Kazmierski, "10Gbit/s for next generation PON with electronic equalization using un-cooled 1.55 μ m directly modulated laser," in *2009 35th European Conference on Optical Communication*, vol. 2009-Supplement pp. 1–2. ISSN: 1550-381X.
13. J. Potet, G. Simon, G. Gaillard, C. Dessemond, F. Saliou, M. Gay, P. Chanclou, and M. Thual, "Uncooled high speed ge/si avalanche photodiode for 50 Gbit/s-PON with 60 km reach," in *2023 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, pp. 1–3.
14. A. Momtaz and M. M. Green, "An 80 mW 40 Gb/s 7-tap t/2-spaced feed-forward equalizer in 65 nm CMOS," pp. 629–639. Conference Name: IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits.
15. R. Boesch, K. Zheng, and B. Murmann, "A 0.003 mm² 5.2 mW/tap 20 GBd inductor-less 5-tap analog RX-FFE," in *2016 IEEE Symposium on VLSI Circuits (VLSI-Circuits)*, pp. 1–2.
16. E. Mammei, F. Loi, F. Radice, A. Dati, M. Bruccoleri, M. Bassi, and A. Mazzanti, "8.3 a power-scalable 7-tap FIR equalizer with tunable active delay line for 10-to-25gb/s multi-mode fiber EDC in 28nm LP-CMOS," in *2014 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference Digest of Technical Papers (ISSCC)*, pp. 142–143. ISSN: 2376-8606.
17. J. Li, Y. Chen, Z. Zhang, H. Wang, C. Guo, and B. Yang, "Group delay compensation by combining 3-tap FFE with CTLE for 80gbps-PAM4 optical transmitter," in *2019 32nd IEEE International System-on-Chip Conference (SOCC)*, pp. 155–160. ISSN: 2164-1706.
18. G. Gaillard, F. Saliou, J. Potet, G. Simon, P. Chanclou, and F. N. Sampaio, "Low bandwidth APD receiver assessment with fixed FIR filter and SOA for multi-rate and several wavelength of class N1 and C+ of higher speed PONs," in *2022 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, pp. 1–4.
19. D. Nasset, I. Cano, G. Simon, F. Saliou, Y. Lin, T. Wettlin, Y. He, and P. Chanclou, "Real-time evaluation of a novel analogue equaliser integrated circuit targeting 50G-PON ONU simplification,".
20. Z. Toprak-Deniz, J. E. Proesel, J. F. Bulzacchelli, H. A. Ainspan, T. O. Dickson, M. P. Beakes, and M. Meghellil, "A 128-gb/s 1.3-pJ/b PAM-4 transmitter with reconfigurable 3-tap FFE in 14-nm CMOS," pp. 19–26.
21. Y. Perelman, Z. Toroker, D. Kumar, E. Maday, N. Familia, T. Carbone, G. Kidron, I. Mizrahi, Y. Landau, R. Saba, Y. Goldberg, and A. Meisler, "A 116-Gb/s PAM4 0.9-pJ/b transmitter with eight-tap FFE in 5-nm FinFET," pp. 2260–2271. Conference Name: IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits.
22. M. Sakib, "Efficient optical front-end for data communications," p. 169.
23. I. Dedic, "56Gs/s ADC : Enabling 100GbE," in *2010 Conference on Optical Fiber Communication (OFC/NFOEC), collocated National Fiber Optic Engineers Conference*, pp. 1–3.
24. O. Eshet, A. Ran, A. Mezer, Y. Hadar, D. Lazar, and M. Moyal, "An adaptive 4-tap analog FIR equalizer for 10-Gb/s over backplane serial link receiver," in *ESSCIRC 2008 - 34th European Solid-State Circuits Conference*, pp. 178–181. ISSN: 1930-8833.
25. D. Chevalier, P. Scalart, G. Simon, L. Bramerie, M. Joindot, J. Potet, M. Gay, P. Chanclou, and M. Thual, "Analog FFE coefficients optimization in 50G-PON using MMSE-based LMS algorithm," in *OSA Advanced Photonics Congress 2024 (2024)*, (Optica Publishing Group).
26. J. Kaiser, "Design methods for sampled data filters," in *Proc. 1st Allerton Conf. Circuit and System Theory*, pp. 221–236.
27. R. Lerner, "Band-pass filters with linear phase," pp. 249–268. Conference Name: Proceedings of the IEEE.
28. G. Simon, J. Potet, D. Chevalier, F. Saliou, P. Chanclou, T. Fujigaki, D. Tanabe, T. Hirayama, Y. Kannan, and L. A. Neto, "High power integrated DFB-EAM-SOA for beyond 35 dB optical path loss 50G-PON and raman scattering estimations," in *50th European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC 2024)*, .
29. J. Potet, M. Gay, L. Bramerie, H. Hallak Elwan, F. Saliou, G. Simon, and P. Chanclou, "Real time 100 Gbit/s/ λ PAM-4 experiments for future access networks over 20 km with 29 dB optical budget," in *2021 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, pp. 1–3.